

Local, National or/and Global? Rethinking Identity through *The Silent Minaret*

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My paper will look at *The Silent Minaret* (2005) by Ishtiyaq Shukri, a South African writer of Indian origin. Set in a period when narrow ethnic and religious nationalisms seem to be in the ascendant in the wake of 9/11 attack and the subsequent “War on Terror,” the novel offers the idea and ideals of cosmopolitanism as an alternative, portraying characters whose commitments go beyond their primary affiliations to a racial, ethnic or religious group. It also probes the meaning of cosmopolitanism with reference to specific sites, especially the city of London, whose status as a cosmopolitan place is shown to be dubious. The contemporary relevance of these questions is attested to by recent developments, such as, the hardening of the British state’s stance on

immigration, evident in its now defunct proposal to deport illegal migrants to Rwanda, and receive 120 million pounds as a part of the deal. Britain also had plans to electronically tag other asylum seekers in order to keep track of their movements.

Whether seen primarily as “a political project” or “an ethical orientation of individuals,” cosmopolitanism describes a certain way of inhabiting the world, particularly with respect to the several others with whom one shares it (Calhoun 2008, 107). It is a relation to both place and people, based on a recognition of diversity and a sense of responsibility towards the diverse others. Cosmopolitanism involves going beyond one’s primary allegiances rooted in ethnicity, nationality etc. towards broader commitments, which is not to deny the significance of the former in an individual’s life or their role as a support system for many; instead, it is to acknowledge the co-existence of plural allegiances none of which should be treated as exclusive. In fact, Kwame Anthony Appiah supports the idea of a cosmopolitanism that is “rooted,” that builds upon one’s ties to a particular place or a particular group of people, which are regarded as “circles among the many circles that are narrower than the human horizon,” each of these circles being an object of one’s “moral concern” (1997, 624). The relevance of cosmopolitanism in the contemporary world is explained by several factors, the foremost among these being the intertwined nature of our political, economic

and cultural lives in a globalized space whose complex nature and concerns cannot be fully addressed through a framework based solely on the nation-state.

While the idea of nation and the discourse on nationalism are omnipresent in different spheres of our everyday life, from educational institutions to different forms of media, claiming us as members of an imagined community, the idea and ideals of cosmopolitanism receive relatively less attention in our collective life. The attempt to address this discrepancy is reflected in calls for “fostering” of cosmopolitanism with the help of “a number of intermediary institutions in public space,” including the media that constitute “obvious sites for stimulating cosmopolitan awareness and highlighting cosmopolitan practices” (Vertovec 2002, 21). Martha Nussbaum’s model of “education for world citizenship” can be seen as one such project (Nussbaum 2002, 15). Its central concern is the “expansion of our ethical horizons” through a “vivid imagining of the different,” that is, those who are not a part of our immediate national/religious/ethnic communities (Nussbaum xiii-xiv, 9). This act of imagination, rooted in facts, is essential to know the other in all its complexity, with respect to its irreducible specificity as well as the underlying commonalities of needs and aspirations. It can also help one realize the limits of one’s own culture and the need to transcend them, which can then form the basis of a compassionate and nuanced response to the other. Literature and art,

in general, can also play an important role in nurturing a cosmopolitan consciousness. The following section of my paper looks at how the novel uses cosmopolitan worldview to reimagine the ensembles that are given, that is, to which one belongs by virtue of birth, such as, family, ethnic/religious groups and nation, especially with reference to the figure of the outsider/immigrant.

Set against the backdrop of the 9/11 attack, *The Silent Minaret* looks at the responses it triggers, the assumptions on which these responses are based and their fallout on the lives of ordinary people. Interestingly, it presents these concerns from the perspective of a group of characters who, except Frances, are South African, and thus belong to a state that is neither the aggressor nor the victim, though two of them, Issa and Katinka, are living in London which plays a key role in the “War on Terror”. Yet these characters, particularly Issa, are profoundly affected by the subsequent developments; in fact, his disappearance is clearly linked to his sense of shock and his mounting frustration with the injustice of the situation. The writer’s choice in terms of focalization makes the readers reflect upon ideas that are central to the novel, such as, the relation between events and people that are distant in time or/and place and the “simultaneous existence of local, national and global identities” (Kurusawa 2004, 239). Thus, the event - the 9/11 attack - may seem remote with seemingly little bearing on their lives as South African nationals, but as “global” citizens, Issa and Katinka are involved, especially as members of the

global South, a group of which Issa considers himself a part. He declares his affiliation in response to his neighbour, Frances's observation that despite being young, he takes the world very seriously, "We southerners have to The only quality of life most of us dare to hope for is after death" (Shukri 2005, 9-10). This community is defined by Issa on the basis of a common history of oppression and dispossession and includes "the Khoi of southern Africa, the aboriginals of Australia, the natives of North America ..." and their descendants (Shukri 2005, 46). Here, South Africa's past and, by implication, its present, are not seen as separate or exceptional but as part of a larger pattern and intertwined with experiences of other places and people.

In her discussion of *The Silent Minaret* Ronit Frenkel (2011, 120) points out that the protagonists' commitments at the global level build upon the sense of self and community forged at the local and national level. Born to a Hindu mother and a Muslim father who abandons his wife before the son is born, Issa grows up in a family which, besides him and his mother, consists of an adoptive mother and brother, Gloria and Kagiso, who are black; it is an arrangement that defies the apartheid state's diktat forbidding intermixing of different racial groups. Religion does not seem to be a major factor in their family life: the boys attend a private Christian school and a festival like Diwali is associated less with the beliefs of a particular religious group than with an

annual ritual of cleaning the house together. As Issa's mother says, "our family is of diverse faiths. Diversity is our normality It's what we nurtured ... home was always, still is, a secular place" (Shukri 2005, 119). Thus, his identity as a part-Muslim remains marginal to Issa's sense of self. Growing up in South Africa in the 1970s and 80s, it is race rather than religion which dominates the boys' sense of themselves and their world. However, although both Issa and Kagiso are keenly aware of the way state sponsored racism distorts their lives and, more so, of those placed more precariously in economic terms, it is Issa whose awareness takes the form of activism and shapes the choices he makes, whether it is his questioning of the one-sided history taught in his school, which erases the contribution of blacks, or joining a protest against the brutal killing of children by the state police. Later, Issa goes on to join the armed wing of the anti-apartheid movement, a fact which his family discovers only after his disappearance.

The anti-apartheid struggle, with its vision of a non-racial South Africa, also provides Katinka an alternative to rethink her identity beyond the confines of the narrow ethnic nationalism supported by her family and propagated by the apartheid state through its institutions, including schools and universities. For instance, Katinka's school uses excursions to historical monuments and other sites of "national" significance to re-present the history of South Africa as the history of one communi-

ty and its achievements and victories. Even the visit to “the site of the first concentration camp . . . designed by Lord Kitchener during the Anglo-Boer War” is selective in its remembrance of the victims: while the “sacrifice” of the Boer women and children who perished in these camps is recalled, there is no mention of the black lives lost in the camps (Shukri 2005, 173). Disturbed by the aggressive nationalism on display on most such occasions and therefore avoiding them, Katinka makes an exception for the visit to the camp, drawn to it by her recent reading of *The Diary of Anne Frank*. She expects to find some recognition of what connects the site to the concentration camps that would be set up in Europe later as a part of the Nazis’ “Final Solution,” but finds none. She is appalled by what she sees as the Afrikaner obsession with their singularity, by the insularity which refuses to acknowledge any commonality of suffering and pain.

Though the formal end of apartheid meant a setback for Afrikaner nationalism, the novel shows how ethnic and religious nationalisms continue to thrive in other places and through other means, post 9/11 London being one such site. In this regard, the writer emphasizes the role played by the state as well as the everyday acts of ordinary citizens. The former invests in and uses symbols such as the national flag and the anthem to promote a certain image of the nation and its destiny among the citizens, to set it apart from and above other nations and

people. Through the characters of Katinka and Frances, who as an Irish Catholic, has been in the position of an outsider herself, the novel draws attention to the divisive potential of such symbols and the unthinking reverence they command. It explains why Katinka wishes to hold on to what she describes as the “stateless moment,” that is, the fleeting interval between coming down of the apartheid state’s flag and hoisting of that of post-apartheid South Africa: “no flag to wave, no anthem to echo, ... no God-chosen nation for which to die in gory glory” (Shukri 2005, 175). The unthinking loyalty towards one’s nation partly depends on what Issa describes as “chronic amnesia,” a failure to engage with or acknowledge certain aspects of the nation’s past which, in Britain’s case, implies its past as a colonial power and its brutal exploitation of the resources of its colonies (Shukri 2005, 111). The country’s enormous material wealth, its hegemony in world affairs, in short, the attributes that supposedly make it great, have their roots in this (in)glorious past. However, for a majority of the citizens, neither the past nor the form in which it resurfaces in the present, affects their relation to their country, which is defined by a sense of unwavering loyalty and belief in Britain’s “exceptionalism”. It is reflected in the passionate singing of “Rule Britannia” – a song with a supremacist, imperialist undertext - by a “bellicose” crowd in London’s Hyde Park (Shukri 2005, 175). These ordinary citizens seem to be utterly oblivious to the unjust war being currently waged overseas by their country, their indifference

to the fate of those affected exposing their complicity. However, some of these distant “others” now share the city and the country with the “natives,” though certainly not as equals. These immigrants perform the menial jobs the latter do not wish to do themselves; while their labor makes life easier, as individuals, they remain invisible, even undesirable. Many of them work in places like the Baghdad Café which Issa and Katinka often visit and, through images flashed on huge screens, witness the bombing of their hometowns in shock and horror as Britain declares its support for the “War on Terror”.

The idea of Britain that emerges through an anthem like “Rule Britannia” is juxtaposed in the novel to the way the country and the city of London, in particular, are perceived and experienced by outsiders like Issa, Katinka as well as Frances, who occupies an in-between space. Even before he is “forced into a new consciousness of himself” by the 9/11 attack and what follows, Issa observes and reflects upon the position of religious and ethnic minorities and immigrants in London (Shukri 2005, 53). One of the things that strikes Issa about his neighbourhood is the silent minaret. As he tells Frances, a silent minaret is like a “blacked-out lighthouse” as its essential function is compromised (Shukri 2005, 57). It reminds him of home and the difference between home and London. The mosque down their road in Johannesburg would call the faithful to prayer five times a day, its sound one among the many sounds that were a part of

their daily life. But in London that sound, its religious and cultural associations, and the difference they signify, are apparently not welcome. The silent minaret may be seen as a forewarning of the events to follow in the wake of 9/11 as mosques in London are barricaded and sealed on the pretext that they are being used to shelter unwanted people. Ironically, it also includes those who have been displaced from their own countries by Britain's overseas misadventures and forced to seek refuge elsewhere. The silence of the minaret thus comes to symbolize the marginalization of a particular religious community on account of its association with those held guilty of the 9/11 bombings. It also stands in stark contrast to the frenzied singing of "Rule Britannia" by the crowd in London's Hyde Park.

In contrast to the increasing hostility with which difference of a certain kind is viewed outside, Frances and Issa together create a space where difference is respected and, if need be, transcended to acknowledge shared ideas and traditions, especially in the realm of faith, a space defined by syncretism in thought and practice. It is in this spirit that Issa offers the gift of tasbeeh to Frances who keeps it in the same pouch as her rosary beads. She does not mind the entanglement of the two strings, which shows that her faith is not defined by the maintenance of boundaries between it and other religions. Both Frances and Issa also cherish the possibilities suggested by the image of the mosque in Durban

which “stands so close to the Catholic cathedral that from certain angles the two buildings almost seem one,” the possibility, for instance, of “a sky that echoes simultaneously with azaan and the Angelus” (Shukri 2005, 58). However, Frances admits the impossibility of the realization of such a dream in contemporary London, a dream which “need[s] to be nurtured with love and respect and not battering rams and riot gear” (Shukri 2005, 58). Here, it may be pointed out that the novel runs the risk of presenting South Africa as more receptive to and tolerant of religious difference than London or the West in general. Though overt demonization of a certain religion may not be noticeable in post-apartheid South Africa, other fault lines do exist. The city of Durban, for instance, was the site of bloody riots in 1948 that targeted the heterogeneous Indian community and there have been other incidents since where other groups have been targeted on account of their ethnicity, nationality etc. but this dimension remains largely unexplored in the novel.

Like Issa, Katinka also tries to engage with people and cultures beyond her own. Estranged from her conservative Afrikaner family, she moves to London where, despite having the “right” credentials in terms of race and language, she does not feel “at home” (Shukri 2005, 190). She is drawn to Karim, a young man from Palestine under whose tutelage she begins to learn Arabic. As a native speaker of English, a world hegemonic lan-

guage, and of Afrikaans, which enjoys a similar status in South Africa, Katinka does not need to know Arabic that is associated with a religious and cultural tradition very different from her own. Yet she makes a serious attempt not only to learn it but also to read the world around her through it, ignoring the familiar signs in English. Learning Arabic also becomes a way of knowing another culture and way of life, and of realizing the limits of one's own. Above all, the act constitutes a rejection of the linguistic nationalism of the Afrikaners, whose embodiment is "Die Taalmonument (the world's only monument to a language)" (Shukri 2005, 173).

Through both these characters the novel articulates what Ronit Frenkel (2011, 120) has described as "a South African produced cosmopolitanism," which is shaped by their life and experiences in South Africa, particularly the struggle against apartheid, wherein they discover the ideals and values to which they commit themselves. These ideals also inform the later actions and choices of the two characters, such as, Katinka's decision to join Karim in Palestine. The experience of his family living in the West Bank under Israel's occupation resonates with her as she had been witness to similar bigotry in South Africa under the apartheid regime. The commonalities between the two contexts are foregrounded through the symbols used to portray them. For instance, Karim's reference to the wall erected by the state of Israel, not only to confine his people, but also to make them "feel small,"

recalls how the racist ideology of the apartheid state was manifested in and through its control of space (Shukri 2005, 146). Similarly, the sight of children growing up in the shadow of war, adept at drawing “helicopter gunships with their eyes closed,” points to the ubiquity of violence that infiltrates all aspects of life, including the innocent games of children; once again, the parallel with the brutalization of children in South Africa’s townships during apartheid is hard to miss (Shukri 2005, 189).

Although the protagonists seek to forge and be part of a wider community, beyond the limits of race and religion, the reality of class and class-based disparities interferes with their aspiration. Issa, in particular, is conscious of the privileges bestowed upon him by his class and education, providing him opportunities which were not available to a majority of South Africa’s non-white population, thus, separating him from those he wishes to make common cause with. For instance, his family’s economic and cultural capital, which enables him to pursue research in London, sets him apart from those he describes as “Europe’s untouchables,” (Shukri 2005, 92) the immigrants who live and work under very different circumstances, not of their own choice, in a city which is, at best, indifferent to their existence. For Issa, their presence is a reminder of the inequalities which persist, in his own country and globally, underlining the fact that the struggle’s not over. It also makes him doubt the value of his research: writing about the past when that past is

still around seems like an indulgence, which is why later, he abandons the manuscript of his thesis on a table in the Baghdad Café. Two incidents, in particular, capture for Issa this sense of the persistence of past and its inequities in the present. The first is the image of suspects arrested in the aftermath of 9/11 attack, “heavily shackled men ... their arms chained behind their backs to their feet,” which recalls a scene from South Africa’s distant past, the arrival of a group of slaves at the Cape Colony in 1694, who also happened to be “shackled in chains ...” (Shukri 2005, 50-51). What links these two sets of men, otherwise distant in time and space is their common status as victims of the European/Western colonial-imperial project, its latest manifestation being the US led aggression after 9/11. The second incident has a more personal resonance for Issa: the sight of police helicopters hovering over the mosque near his flat in London brings back memories of a similar offensive launched by the South African state to flush out anti-apartheid student-activists from Issa’s university.

Both the novel and Issa’s research can be read as attempts to assert the “reality of global cross-pollination and intermingling” that have played a crucial role in the evolution of nations and societies, political and religious communities, but have been systematically erased by states in their pursuit of an “inviolable national identity” and by religious heads who dismiss evidence of overlap between faiths in their obsession with points of differ-

ence (Shukri 2005, 47). The suppression of this “hybrid dynamic” results in histories of nations being written as histories of single communities with the latter’s debt to other groups and their relations of interdependence finding little or no mention (Shukri 2005, 47). In this context, one may also think of the work of Achille Mbembe (2017,104) who argues that it is the phenomenon of “worlds in movement” that has defined life in Africa. It refers to the movement of diverse groups of people into the continent at different points of time, such as the Afrikaners who settled in South Africa or the indentured labour brought in from India, as well as those who left or were displaced like the large number of enslaved blacks. It also takes cognizance of the internal dispersal of populations in pre-colonial Africa as people left their place of origin to settle elsewhere for reasons as varied as wars, marriage etc. Mbembe (2017, 104-105) argues that these multiple histories of “itinerancy, displacement and mobility” have produced a “blending, mixing and superimposing” of cultures in Africa. The contexts in which these histories unfolded, and the relations between different groups, were often unequal, and marred by violence, which meant that the experience of “interweaving” was a more painful and torturous one for some of them than for the others (Mbembe 2017, 105).

Issa’s research focuses on this aspect of early seventeenth-century European settlement in Southern Afri-

ca, drawing attention to the transnational and transcultural exchanges that shaped the subsequent history of the place and its people (Frenkel 2011). One of these was the movement of slaves from different parts of the Dutch empire in South and Southeast Asia to the Cape. Most of these slaves were Muslims and came to be known as Cape Malays (Shukri 2005, 51). Later, the Cape was also used as a penal colony where political prisoners and dissenters from the Dutch empire were held. Among these was Sheikh Yusuf of Macassar, deported to the Cape around 1694-95, who is supposed to have been instrumental in organizing resistance to the Dutch colonizers, besides establishing the presence of Islam in the region. Thus, the history of South Africa, especially the history of the struggle against colonial rule, is presented as having been built upon the contribution and sacrifices of various groups, including the Cape Malays. Moreover, by foregrounding events and figures from the past that are little known outside a certain community, Issa's research and the novel try to give them their due place in the nation's history, and make that history more inclusive and representative: thus, 1994 ought to be remembered not only as the year of South Africa's first democratic elections but also as "the tri-centenary of Islam in the country" (Shukri 2005, 53). These narratives about South African Muslims, serve to counter demonization of Islam, as Ronit Frenkel also points out in her discussion of the novel. However, it is important to note that Issa, the protagonist, does not self-identify

(primarily) as a Muslim. If verses from the Quran are kept in his room in London, so are quotations from diverse secular writings, the pride of place being reserved for the five-volume Truth and Reconciliation Commission report, all of them equally important for his moral growth, for shaping his convictions. In fact, his sense of community is defined first and foremost in terms of the struggle against apartheid and evolves in response to recognition of wider solidarities at the global scale. Thus, his response to the “War on Terror” is not determined by the religious identity of the victims, which he happens to share. (There is little evidence in the novel to support the idea that Issa’s disappearance is linked to his radicalization. For one, none of the figures who inspired him, including Mandela and Che Guevara, saw the world through the prism of religion and religious difference). But in post 9/11 London, Issa’s identity becomes synonymous with his religion, at least in the eyes of the British state, which explains his detention at Heathrow. His initial reaction is one of shock and disbelief that such a thing could be happening to him. In response to a fellow detainee’s comment on his name, “In here we all have such names,” Issa wants to protest that he is “different” (Shukri 2005, 126). The difference lies in his sense of his identity as plural, not reducible to any of the narrow labels/categories through which the state sees and judges people. Till this point, Issa’s class had afforded him some measure of protection against the worst forms of discrimination, in South Africa under the apartheid re-

gime as well as London, but in a post 9/11 world divided sharply along lines of religion, it is rendered irrelevant as Issa and all other followers of Islam are lumped together, and treated as a homogeneous entity, which is supposedly susceptible to extremism and intolerant of the liberal values of the global North. Ironically, among the first casualties of the “War on Terror” are these same liberal values, including the ideals of cosmopolitanism, embodied by the novel’s protagonists.

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